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Influence of Religious Inclination, School Type and Attitude on Upper Basic Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour in Edo and Delta States

Akhogbai, E. M¹, Ogheneakoke, E. C² Dania, P. O³
¹²³Delta State University, Abraka

ABSTRACT

This study examined the influence of religious inclination, school type and attitude on Upper Basic Social Studies Students sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. Three research questions were raised and three null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. This study adopted a Descriptive Survey Research Design on a population of fifty-one thousand, six hundred and twenty-four and a sample size of 720 respondents was employed via the multi-stage sampling technique. Findings of the study revealed amongst others that, there was no significant relationship between religious inclination and school type and Upper Basic Social Studies Students towards sexual behaviour. There was a significant relationship of Upper Basic Social Studies Students' attitude towards sexual behaviour. The study concluded that religious inclination and school type does not influence Upper basic Social Studies students sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States; and that the attitude of Upper Basic Social Studies students influences their sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. The study made recommendations accordingly.

KEYWORDS

Religious Inclination, School Type, Attitude, Social Studies, Sexual Behaviour.

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Introduction

Students' sexual behavior has become increasingly problematic in recent years. The number of Nigerian students engaging in coital and premarital sex is rising. It seems that students in social studies programs today place a higher value on sex than their predecessors did, which, if left unchecked, will inevitably result in issues for young people in the community. More than a million teenagers get pregnant, 65 percent gave birth to children outside of marriage, according to Samuel and Sanusi (2019). This underscores the need to monitor students' sexual behavior. Similarly Nigussie et al. (2020), determined that sexual behaviour, which is largely responsible for the growth and progress of society, causes 2.5 to 5 million adolescents to contract STDs annually. Implicit here is that an unchecked conduct of students is a disaster waiting to happen due to the pace at which society is moving.

The fast pace of social change has displaced long-standing traditions regarding the sexual conduct of students. Students' premarital sexual involvement was previously reduced by customs; however, today's students display their sexual behavior in a variety of ways. According to Nigussie et al. (2020), secondary school students engage in a variety of sexual behaviors. These include oral sex, hand holding, touching one another's genital organ through clothing, and physical contact below the neck. Adolescent students, including those studying social studies, are distinguished by specific background characteristics that are increasingly influencing their levels of erotic behaviour. These characteristics warrant further study and comprehension.

A student's religious preferences can influence their unhealthy behavior and inaction regarding sexual behavior. Conventional reasoning is linked to following social norms and social justice. Teenage sexual activity is discouraged by both societal norms and religious teachings. This suggests that religious teenagers have a higher cognitive likelihood of forming attitudes and values that moderate teenage sexual behavior. Psychologists concur that socialization and beliefs affect how people behave. As a result, religion, as a social agent, has a significant impact on how teenagers in a particular society believe and behave. Kiboi (2018) posits that an individual's religious inclination can limit their attitudes towards engaging in sexual activities. Teenagers' sexual debuts appear to be postponed by religion. According to research by Bearman and Brückner (2015), people who regularly engaged in religious activities postponed their first sexual experience more often than people who did not. Kiboi (2018) asserts that religious institutions, such as churches, have significant social and cultural influence and that they teach and control sexual behavior in a community. The impact of religious affiliation on teenage premarital sexual behavior was studied by Zaidi et al. (2014), who found a causal link between the two. Teenagers who identify as members of specific religious groups therefore tend to abstain from having sex before marriage. Kiboi also discovered that adolescents who attended religious meetings in Nigeria had a higher likelihood of this restricting effect of religious inclination on premarital sex. Meetings may take the shape of schools run and owned by the numerous religious organizations that exist throughout the nation.

There is a relationship between the type of school and the sexual behavior of the students. Because they are surrounded by people of the opposite sex, students at mixed-gender institutions are more likely to engage in more sexual activity. Additionally, the social milieu in which today's teenagers are raised is far more accepting of sexuality than their parents were (Onyesom&Igberaharha, 2021). The best ways to comprehend the detrimental effects of this circumstance on teenagers' sexual behavior and health are through research and other firsthand accounts (Ekanem, 2021). According to Ekanem, teenage sexual activity is very common among Nigerian teenagers, which contributes to high rates of adolescent pregnancy, school dropout,

academic under achievement, abortions, maternal mortality, and infection with STDs like HIV/AIDS. This generally conveys the idea that a large number of teenagers engage in self-destructive behavior. Many teenagers still have a lot of misconceptions about sexual relationships. One of the main factors assisting in the emancipation from parents seems to be identification with peers. Such identification compels the child to follow advice given by peers their own age in their quest for emancipation. Premarital sex may be an attempt to give in to peer group pressure, according to Ekanem (2021). According to Seventeen Magazine (2008), the primary information source for high school students engaged in sexual activities is their peer group. Teenagers who have never had sex want to try it out too, especially when they hear from their friends that it's enjoyable. Hence, one setting where peer group influence is particularly strong is school. The kind of school a student attends has an impact on both their behavior and learning opportunities. There have been arguments made in favor of and against coeducational and single-sex schools, and a lot of research has been done on the subject of school type—mostly in relation to academic performance.

On the other hand, Ajuwon et al. (2006) concentrated on sexual behavior in connection to school type. Among secondary school students in three states in North Eastern Nigeria, the researchers examined sexual behavior and the experience of sexual coercion. They discovered that students attending boys-only schools had a significantly higher likelihood of having engaged in sexual activity (18%) compared to students attending coeducational and girls-only schools (14% and 2%, respectively). The main factors that were found to predict sexual activity were having a boy/girl friend, living arrangement, age, sex, type of school, and school location (Igberaharha, 2014; Igberaharha&Onyesom, 2021). It was discovered that there was more sexual activity among respondents who attended coeducational schools in metropolitan areas and who had friends who were both male and female. More precisely, respondents attending coeducational schools reported higher rates of sexual activity than respondents attending single-sex schools. In addition, it was discovered that sex and school type could predict sexual coercion. Sexual coercion was a common occurrence among the subjects of the survey. In all, 5.1% of the pupils reported having experienced rape. It is also important to note that the majority of students, including those studying social studies, imitate characters and try to test out what they have seen or heard in the media on their peers, which increases the prevalence of sexual acts in coed institutions. The entertainment and education provided by mass media is crucial, and it is important to assess how much teenagers absorb from these platforms. The majority of students mimic and experiment with what they see and hear in the media, disregarding the negative effects this has on both themselves and society as a whole. Teenagers replicate and experiment with shows that are aired or shown, making the mass media a true conduit for the dissemination of knowledge and information to its audience. These teen years where a person can easily fall into social deviations, especially deviations. These days, the mass media and electronic media both disseminate a lot of false information regarding sex (Daryantiet al. 2021). Igberaharha (2016) agreed to the influence of technology in his assertion that due to the proliferation of pornographic VCDs and the sophistication of Internet technology that disseminates numerous pornographic websites, 900 thousand Indonesian teenagers undergo abortions annually as a result of adolescent free sex associations. Numerous sexual assault victims discuss emotional stimuli that they experienced as a result of emotionally charged scenes in popular media, including magazines, books, films, television, and cellphones. Pornography lowers moral standards, stimulates the sex organs, and promotes sexual behavior (Keller & Brown, 2016). One teacher revealed that many students had files containing pornography on their cell phones when they were held, based on the findings of an initial study. Subsequently, twenty students were given questionnaires concerning their sexual behavior and the use of electronic media; they responded in writing on the accompanying answer sheets.

According to the findings of an initial investigation, numerous students had files containing porn when their cell phones were in their hands, as reported by a teacher. After receiving question sheets regarding their use of electronic media and their sexual behavior, twenty students wrote their responses on the accompanying answer sheets.

One essential and determining component of students' sexuality is their attitude toward sexual behavior. There is a clear differentiation made between attitudes toward sexual behavior that are positive, or erotophilic, and those that are negative, or erotophobic. According to Bourke et al. (2014), sexuality is defined and determined by an individual's willingness to respond to sexual stimuli across a positive-negative spectrum. These two extremes represent the ends of this continuum. According to Heras et al. (2016), individuals who exhibit more erotophilic attitudes tend to be more open to different forms of sexual behavior, including masturbation, and to experience higher levels of sexual satisfaction. According to Heras et al. (2016), they have been noted to typically develop a reassured form of attachment with their partners, characterized by a clear orientation towards love, enjoyment of the erotic experience, and communication and expression of positive emotions. Reis et al. (2011) found that attitudes of this kind, which are held by both genders, are linked to lower risk sexual behavior, such as the use of preservatives, because they are more favorable toward contraceptive methods or more successful strategies for preventing sexually transmitted infections (STIs).

In Nigeria, a wide range of stakeholders have expressed interest in the trend of teenage sexual behaviour due the proliferation of STIs in the society that is not abating in the foreseeable future. Through a variety of campaigns featuring catchphrases like "sex is worth waiting for, Zip up," among others, the various parties involved have been working to curb these sexual behaviors among Nigerian teenagers and students. While some others have arranged seminars and workshops, it appears that these are not producing many outcomes. Therefore, it's imperative to thoroughly investigate the impact of religious inclination, school type and attitudes of Upper Basic Social Studies students regarding sexual behaviour in the Edo and Delta States.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

- i. What is the relationship between religious inclination and Upper Basic Social Studies student towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States?
- ii. What is the relationship between school type and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States?
- iii. What is the relationship between attitude and Upper Basic Social Studies students' towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

- i. There is no significant relationship between religious inclination and Upper Basic Social Studies student towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between school type and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States.
- iii. There is no significant relationship between attitude and Upper Basic Social Studies students' towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States.

Religious Inclination and Students' Sexual Behaviour

Regular research on religious inclination typically demonstrates the relationship between religious adaptation measures and markers of health and well-being in both individuals and groups, as well as levels of sexual behavior. Researchers use these studies as a basis for developing interventions to help adolescents adjust to their sexuality. Religion has been linked in numerous studies in that field to helping students exercise self-control when it comes to their sexual behavior (Luhmann, 2020). Luhmann defined religion as a search for meaning connected to the sacred and discovered that for many people, including Social Studies students, it becomes an essential component of their meaning systems. It provides a particular perspective from which to understand the world, interpersonal relationships, and human behavior in general, including sexual behavior. Particularly in more emotional and psychological situations, religion's capacity to provide meaning and purpose appears to be correlated with its ability to help people cope.

According to other research, such as Jung's (2015), students' sexual behavior can be moderated by their belief in God through an internal mediator that works similarly to how social relationships function. Therefore, individuals with high levels of religious belief may perceive God as a secure haven, a person with whom they can form intense attachments, similar to those formed with parents, a loving God who is perceptive of believers' needs and actively involved in human affairs. All of these give people a feeling of closeness and confidence in God, which is consoling in difficult circumstances, such as engaging in sexual activity. On the other hand, people who have heightened awareness of sin and sinfulness—which is frequently accompanied by feelings of moral inferiority and personal deprivation—may exhibit reduced levels of life satisfaction (Jung, 2015).

Hisham and Pargament (2015) state that a large number of people from all religious traditions rely on spiritual practices, teachings, and beliefs to overcome sexual challenges, change their viewpoints, and find comfort. According to Pearce et al. (2017), numerous studies have suggested that prayer can effectively manage anxiety and sexual behavior.

According to Loveth and Isoken (2020), church teachings are likely to influence how people form their attitudes, values, and decisions because religious values serve as the basis for moral guidelines for a large number of people. However, the degree to which religion affects a person's sexual behavior depends on the particular doctrines and policies of the churches as well as the degree to which a person is integrated into and committed to their particular religious institution (Moon, 2021).

Religious groups within Christianity are strongly against premarital sex; however, Pentecostal and Evangelical movements are particularly strong in this regard. While these movements have the power to excommunicate offending members, the former can overlook such behavior in the hopes that the offending individuals will change (Bialystok & Wright, 2019). Expectations of individual Catholics and Evangelical Protestants being less accepting of premarital sex than non-fundamentalist Protestants stem from this differential institutional commitment to sexual behavior; however, the majority of denominations now adhere to the "don't ask don't tell" doctrine. The likelihood of accepting and participating in unhealthy sexual behavior is higher among those who do not identify as religious. Given that the majority of religious groups forbid having sex before marriage, the level of devotion to religious institutions may have a greater influence on premarital sexual behavior than religious affiliation.

Religious messages opposing immoral sexual behavior may be delivered more frequently to those who attend religious services. They may also be more inclined to accept the premarital sex teachings of their religious institutions due to their stronger religious commitment. Therefore, people who value religion and regularly attend religious services are probably more likely than others to adopt sexual behaviors that are compliant with their religious beliefs. Thus, compared to young people who are less involved in religious institutions, those who are active in religious groups would either be more committed to sexual abstinence prior to marriage or would place more value on maturity in sexual relationships (Vasilenko, 2017).

Participating in religious organizations would also increase the likelihood that young people would make friends with peers who view premarital sex as restrictive. Adolescents involved in religious activities are more likely to interact with adults who could potentially influence them to postpone having sex. People's values and actions with regard to family and personal matters can have an impact on their religious commitment. People whose beliefs conflict with those of their religious organizations can reconcile these differences in a number of ways, such as by redefining the group's stance on a particular issue or changing their opinions to better reflect their faith. There would be no essential effect on the person's religious commitment in any of these scenarios. It follows from these theoretical considerations that there should be a reciprocal causal relationship between teenage sexual behavior and religious commitment.

According to Beekers and Schrijvers (2020), the Islamic faith is unyielding in its morality toward sexuality. They follow the divine instruction to "avoid getting close to adultery, Lo!" The meaning of "It is an abomination and an evil way" is to stay away from any circumstances or behaviors that could result in adultery. Keeping boyfriends and girlfriends is one example of this. Interacting freely with people of the other sex by going to parties and doing western-style dancing, going to places where people of the other sex congregate, and, for a woman, dressing provocatively in street harlot attire. The writers came to understand that the Islamic faith holds that the only sexual unions that Allah approves of are those that occur during a valid marriage. According to Rogers (2017), "human behavior is not mechanical but unpredictable." Information delivery that may develop intentions may not always result in behavior, so it cannot be examined using a push-button functions approach. There might be things that stand in the way of the intentions behind the actions and create a negative relationship between the dissemination of information and behavioral changes in the classroom that students have to deal with on a daily basis. According to Jung (2015), a setting with both male and female presence-a school-is more likely to have this kind of circumstance.

School Type and Students' Sexual Behaviour

In this context, "school type" refers to a single- or mixed-gender educational facility. Depending on the school's inclination, it may be an all-male, all-female, or mixed school. Regarding their sexual behavior, these schools' students have differing perspectives from one another. Prior to the 20th century, single-sex education was widely used, especially in secondary and postsecondary education. Across the world, single-sex education is prevalent due to custom and religious beliefs. Due to educational research, there has been a recent surge in interest and the creation of single-sex schools (Riordan, 2009).

Most school administrators are now exploring co-educational education, although single-sex education is still implemented in many Muslim majority areas and mission schools. Since these students are a blend of male and female, they are more likely to engage in sexual activities and adopt sexual postures. This can have an impact on how each student learns, discusses, and observes others'

displays of sexuality in the classroom. Teachers in the schools are not exempt either; in the case of mixed classes, male teachers in particular are observed showing favoritism toward one sex over another, thereby influencing students' sexual behavior. According to Smith and Harrison (2013), research conducted in South African secondary schools found that both male and female educators were perceived as consistently reproducing gender norms in their interactions with students and other staff members, potentially promoting risky sexual behavior within the school. These unequal power relations and gender norms have also been linked to the sexual harassment of girls by male teachers in the school setting, according to numerous studies (Robbinson et al., 2017).

The kind of school a student attends has an impact on both their behavior and learning opportunities. There have been arguments made in favor of and against coeducational and single-sex schools, and a lot of research has been done on the subject of school type—mostly in relation to academic performance. On the other hand, Ajuwon et al. (2006) concentrated on sexual behavior in connection to school type. The study examined sexual behavior and the experience of sexual coercion among secondary school students in three states in Northeastern Nigeria. The results showed that students attending boys-only schools had a significantly higher likelihood of having engaged in sexual activity (18%) compared to students attending coeducational and girls-only schools (14% and 2%, respectively). The main factors that were found to predict sexual activity were having a boy/girl friend, living arrangement, age, sex, type of school, and school location. It was discovered that there was more sexual activity among respondents who attended coeducational schools in metropolitan areas and who had friends who were both male and female.

More specifically, compared to respondents in single-sex schools, those in coeducational schools were more likely to have engaged in sexual activity. Predictors of sexual coercion were also found to be related to sex and school type. The phenomenon of sexual coercion was prevalent among the surveyed population. Five percent of the students had experienced sexual assault. Their study on sexual behavior in coeducational schools supports the finding that, even in American coeducational institutions, girls experience sexual harassment. According to Seventeen Magazine's (2008) findings on sexual harassment, 89% of the 2000+ respondents had experienced inappropriate touching and comments at school.

Attitude of Students and Sexual Behaviour

Intimacy and sexual behavior are universal phenomena that are greatly impacted by individual fantasies and orientations. Additionally, societies, their histories, and their cultures have a significant impact on attitudes regarding sex, sexuality, orientation, and reproduction. These identities inevitably affect the way we think and how our attitudes develop, as well as our latent and manifest world views. Deviance and normalcy in a wide range of human behaviors are determined by societies and cultures. This relationship defines acceptable behavior norms and acceptable deviations through a complex interaction of factors (Ayonrinde, 2015). The spectrum of aberrant sexual behaviors that were once referred to as sexual deviance, perversions, or aberrations are now called paraphilias. The Greek term "paraphilia," which has less derogatory connotations, means "beyond or irregular" (para) and "a love of" (philia) than previously used names.

Formal sex education in schools is rare or nonexistent in many developing nations, including Nigeria; when it does exist, it is typically found to be insufficient. Unprotected sex, unplanned pregnancies, and STDs are frequently caused by inadequate sex education (Kar et al., 2015). Adolescents who engage in coital and non-coital sexual behaviors run the risk of experiencing unfavorable outcomes like pregnancy and the acquisition of STDs. Health care providers need to be

aware of the evolving trends in adolescent sexual behavior in order to provide this population with the necessary medical care and education (WHO, 2017).

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Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Each and every Upper Basic II Social Studies student enrolled in public secondary schools in Delta and Edo States were the study's population. Twenty-one thousand, five hundred and sixty-four (21,564) for Delta and thirty thousand and sixty (30,060) for Edo are the figures provided by the Edo and Delta States Ministries of Education (2022). The researcher used a multi-stage sampling approach. The researcher employed two different sample techniques, hence the sampling technique is required. Structured questionnaire was constructed for the collection of data from Social Studies students. The collated data were analyzed using the simple correlation and regression statistics at an alpha of 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Questions 1: What is the relationship between religious inclination and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States? Result is presented in Table 1

Table 1: Simple Correlation Analysis of Religious Inclination and Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour

Variables	N	r	r ²	r ^{2adj}
Religious Inclination				
Social Studies students sexual behaviour	720	.012	.000	-.001

Independent Variable: Religious Inclination, Dependent Variable: Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour

Table 1 presents the simple correlation results where it was revealed that religious inclination as indicated by r-value of .012 showed a positive relationship between religious inclination of Social Studies students and their sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. This provides an answer to research question 1. It revealed that there exists a positive relationship between religious inclination and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. The r² adjusted value of -.001 indicates that religious inclination of students has no impact on their sexual behaviour in the area under review.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between religious inclination and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. In order to test hypothesis 1, simple regression was computed. The summary of the output is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Simple Regression Analysis of the relationship between Religious Inclination and Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Score ($\bar{x}$)	F	t	Std Error	Sig
Regression	2.071	1	2.071	.108	.328	.38	.74
Residual	13594.353	719	19.201				
Total	13596.424	720					

$P \geq 0.05$ level of significance; $N = 720$

As shown in Table 2, the computed ANOVA produced an $F = .108$, $P \geq 0.05$. Therefore the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between religious inclination and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour was accepted. The finding is that there is no significant relationship between religious inclination and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour. The conclusion is reached that religious inclination has no positive contribution to sexual behaviour of students involved in this study.

Research Questions 2: What is the relationship between school type and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States?

Table 3: Simple Correlation Analysis of School Type and Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour

Variables	N	r	r ²	r ^{2adj}
School Type				
Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour	720	.021	.000	-.001

Independent Variable: School Type, Dependent Variable: Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour.

Table 3 presents the simple correlation results. It revealed that school type as indicated by r-value of .021 shows a positive relationship between it and Social Studies students sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. This provides an answer to research question 2. It revealed that there is a positive relationship between school type and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. The r² adjusted value of -.001 indicated that school type has no impact on Upper Basic Social Studies Students sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between school type and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. In order to test hypothesis 2, simple regression was computed. The summary of the output is presented in table 4.

Table 4: Simple Regression Analysis of the relationship between school type and Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	t	Std Error	Sig
Regression	13590.466	1	5.958	.310	-.557	.330	.58
Residual	13596.424	719	19.196				
Total	13596.424	720					

P ≥ 0.05 level of significance; N = 720

As shown in Table 4, the computed ANOVA produced an F = .310, P ≥ 0.05. Therefore the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between school type and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States was accepted. The finding is that there is no significant relationship between school type and sexual behaviour of Upper Basic Social Studies students’ sexual behaviour. The conclusion is reached that school type has no positive contribution to sexual behaviour of students involved in this study.

Research Questions 3: What is the relationship between attitude and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States?

Table 5: Simple Correlation Analysis of Attitude and Social Studies Students sexual Behaviour

Variables	N	r	r ²	r ^{2adj}
Attitude				
Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour	720	.099	.010	.008

Independent Variable: Attitude, Dependent Variable: Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour

Table 5 presents the simple correlation results. It revealed that attitude as indicated by r–value of .099 shows a positive relationship between attitude and Upper Basic Social Studies Students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. This provides an answer to research question 3 which revealed that there is a linear positive relationship between attitude and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. The r² adjusted value of .008 indicated that attitude has impact on Social Studies students sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between attitude and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. In order to test hypothesis 3, simple regression was computed. The summary of the output is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Simple Regression Analysis of the relationship between Attitude and Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour

Model	Sum Square	df	Mean Score	f	t	Std Error	Sig
Regression	133.534	1	133.534	7.022	-2.650	.341	.01

Residual	13462.890	719	19.015
Total	13596.424	720	

$P \leq 0.05$ level of significance; $N = 720$

As shown in Table 6, the computed ANOVA produced an $F = 7.022$, $P \leq 0.05$. Therefore the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between attitude and Upper Basic Social Studies Students towards sexual behaviour was rejected. The finding is that there is a significant relationship between attitude and Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. The conclusion is reached that attitude has positive correlation to sexual behaviour of student involved in this study.

Discussion

The first hypothesis's result showed that there was no discernible link between Upper Basic Social Studies students' religious inclination and their attitudes toward sexual behavior. This suggests that students studying social studies are not affected by their religious beliefs in terms of their sexual behavior. This study contradicts the findings of Jung (2015), who noted that through a process akin to that which occurs in social relationships, a student's belief in God can act as an internal mediator to moderate their sexual behavior. Noting that individuals with high levels of religiosity may perceive God as a loving, caring being who is attuned to the needs of believers, a place of refuge where intense attachment feelings converge, similar to those formed with parents, and involved in human affairs, and by extension reducing students indulgence in sexual behaviour which can at best be detrimental to their self - health and academics in general.

The present study supports the findings of Hisham and Pargament (2015), who suggested that a significant number of individuals across all religious traditions depend on spiritual teachings, beliefs, and practices to overcome sexual challenges, change their perspectives, and find comfort; thus, supporting the influence of religious inclination on students. Everything suggests that prayer can effectively reduce anxiety and control sexual behavior, as suggested by numerous studies. The study also supported the findings of Loveth and Isoken (2020), who noted that religious beliefs play a role in preventing sexual fantasies. They noted that since religious beliefs serve as a source of moral guidance for many people, church teachings are likely to influence how people form their attitudes, values, and decisions, sexual behavior inclusive. Noting further that the degree of integration and commitment that people have to their specific religious institutions, as well as the specific doctrines and policies of the churches, determine how much religion influences individual sexual behavior (Moon, 2021). Despite this, their research suggests that students' sexual behavior in Social Studies is influenced by their religious beliefs.

Although the opposition to premarital sex is more extreme among Pentecostal and Evangelical religious movements, Bialystok and Wright's (2019) study confirms the findings of the current study regarding the strong opposition of Christian religious groups against it. While the former can put up with the offending members in the hopes that they will change, the latter can punish their members by excommunication. Because the Social Studies students are fully aware of the consequences of engaging in sexual behavior, their religious belief and understanding can serve as a restraint.

Compared to their nonreligious classmates, students who identify as religious talk about sexual topics less frequently, but they also talk more about abstinence and are less comfortable and willing to discuss sexual things with friends.

Students who identify as religious also seem to be more conservative in their attitudes around sexuality and behavior, and it seems that this conservatism extends to their conversations with peers. Similar findings were made by Robinson et al. (2017), who discovered that male teachers harass girls in the classroom more often than female teachers. This is linked to uneven power dynamics and gender stereotypes, which in turn promote dangerous sexual conduct in schools. They observed that students' educational opportunities and, in turn, their behavior are influenced by the kind of school they attend.

It was shown that students attending boys-only schools were far more likely (18%) to have had sex than students attending coeducational schools (14%), girls-only schools (2%), and both. Two significant predictors of sexual activity were found to be attending a certain type of school and having a male or female buddy. The respondents with coeducational urban schools and mixed-gender friends were shown to have greater rates of sexual engagement.

According to the results of hypothesis seven, attitudes about sexual behavior among Upper Basic Social Studies students and attitudes were significantly correlated. This research suggests that students' attitudes about social studies do have an impact on their sexual behavior. This result was consistent with the research by Adiaha et al. (2018), which proposed that students' attitudes toward sexual behavior in the classroom are influenced by their self-perception. They observed that teenage students had generally positive views regarding sexual behavior, with female students having more positive views than male students.

Furthermore, the results of the current study are consistent with those of Arop et al. (2019), who examined adolescents' attitudes toward sex education and perception management in secondary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria, and discovered a significant relationship between students' attitudes and their sexual fantasies and behavior in the classroom. The investigation by Omozuwa and Aisien (2019) on sexual behavior and attitudes toward sexual behavioral outcomes among Edo State secondary school students was also consistent with the findings of this study. Among other things, their research showed that males were more sex-exploitative than females during the adolescent years. In contrast, the results of the current study contradict those of Hareh's (2014) study, which found no evidence of a significant correlation between students' attitudes and their sexual behavior. This study made clear that students' attitudes have no bearing whatsoever on their sexual behaviour.

Conclusion

The study concluded that:

- i. In Edo and Delta States, students studying Upper Basic Social Studies, sexual behavior is not influenced by religious inclination.
- ii. In Edo and Delta States, the style of school has no bearing on the sexual behavior of Upper Basic Social Studies students.
- iii. Students' attitudes on sexual behavior in Edo and Delta States are influenced by their Upper Basic Social Studies coursework.

Recommendations

Following from the conclusion, the following recommendations were made that to prevent unintended consequences, pregnancies and STDs, Upper Basic Social Studies students should regularly receive education on safe behavioral approaches to sex and sexual outcomes from their religious setting and school authorities should as a matter of urgency institute a system of regular indoctrination of adolescents with a view to informing them of the dangers inherent in unsafe sexual conduct.

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